

THE METHODOLOGY FOR EDUCATING THE QUALITY OF AGILITY OF YOUNG TABLE TENNIS PLAYERS

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Annotation : This article discusses the importance of training athletes who have started playing table tennis, the quality of dexterity. It is also widely reported that the quality of dexterity helps participants to master technical and tactical skills well.

Keywords: physical, functional, technical and tactical, fundamental, psychological, dexterity, flexibility, psychomotor.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается важность обучения спортсменов, которые начали играть в настольный теннис, качеству ловкости. Также широко освещается тот факт, что качество ловкости помогает участникам хорошо овладевать техническими и тактическими навыками.

Ключевые слова: физический, функциональный, технико-тактический, фундаментальный, психологический, ловкость, гибкость, психомоторный.

The search for ways to regularly improve the training process in various branches of training athletes in our country, to determine the most effective ways to form the knowledge, skills and qualifications of those involved, as well as to bring the table tennis players of our country to the world arena, and the training of highly qualified table tennis players are current problems today. Therefore, it is of particular importance for athletes who have started playing table tennis to form vital movements and skills, to develop their physical qualities.

The speed and complexity of movements in table tennis players is the first measure of agility. If the spatial, temporal, force characteristics of the action correspond to the action task, the action becomes clear enough, the action tasks give rise to the concept of the accuracy of the action.

Let's get acquainted with the methods of developing the quality of agility in the training process. In small and middle-aged practitioners, the quality of agility can be most effectively brought up. During this period, the ability to master movement skills, vision, hearing, sensation with the skin and the rapid development of other analyzers are observed. Exercises that develop the quality of agility in table tennis players are performed at the beginning of the main part of training and in the preparatory part. Because the development of agility in a tired state has little effect. Firstly, the development of the quality of agility consists in training the ability to perform coordination-complex actions, and secondly, to reconfigure the activity of movement in accordance with the requirements of suddenly changed conditions. In this, it is important to clearly perceive one's own movements necessary for agility in space and time, if necessary, to be able to make stable movements, to be able to maintain balance, to exert alternating tension and relax muscles, or, on the contrary, to selectively improve the ability to tense muscles and other similar features. Hence "agility" means the sum of the total set of coordination of movements.

The degree of its development is determined by the level of development of psychomotor capabilities involved in solving complex-coordination issues. The main ways to develop and train agility is to form a new variety of movement skills and skills. This causes the reserve of movement skills to increase and does not remain without an effective effect on the functionality of movement analyzers. Even if it is planned to learn new movements at long intervals, students are advised to do exercises that are not known to them from time to time. Because if new moves are not mastered, it becomes more difficult for the practitioner to perform rapid technical and tactical moves against the opponent's moves in the competition processes. It is not necessary to fully master such exercises, since it is necessary for those involved to feel some new movement. In the development of the quality of agility, any involuntary movement can be used as the ability to master new movements, but they are studied only because they are new elements in the composition of the exercise. As you acquire skills, the

importance of this physical exercise in the style of a tool for the development of agility begins to decrease. The ability to quickly and purposefully restructure the activity of movement indicates that an immediate response to effects in suddenly changed conditions is developing agility. In this, a change in the load occurs, increasing the load directed towards the development of agility increases coordination difficulties for those involved. The coordination difficulties they must overcome will consist of the following requirements:

- a) Difficulties in achieving the accuracy of movements;
- b) Difficulties in their ability to adapt;
- d) The tortures that are encountered in short, changed circumstances at once.

One of the qualities of agility that is relatively private is the study and improvement of being able to relax muscles rationally. Any movement is, in a certain sense, the result of the excitation and relaxation of the muscles. Like agitation, knowing relaxation plays an important roll when performing any action effectively. The tension of the group of muscles, which must be temporarily relaxed to perform the movement admirably, eliminates the bullshit necessary to perform the movement, free execution of the movement.

Exercises aimed at developing agility lead to relatively rapid fatigue, while doing these exercises requires the muscles to feel extremely clearly and have little effect when fatigue occurs. Therefore, in the training of agility, rest intervals are used, which are sufficient for a relatively complete recovery. And the exercises are tried to be performed at times when there are practically no symptoms of fatigue after previous loads.

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